

Synthesis of cross-linked graft copolymer from styrene sulphonate monomer and poly(vinyl alcohol) and study of its lead ion binding capacity

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Abstract : Cross-linked graft copolymer has been synthesized through graft copolymerization of styrene sulphonate onto poly(vinyl alcohol) and then cross-linking it with the help of glutaraldehyde. The copolymer is characterized by spectral and thermal analysis. Physical characteristics such as bulk density, particle size, surface area, cross-link density, pore size and percentage of grafting have been evaluated. Metal ion binding capacity of the synthesized material is studied in terms of pH of the medium, temperature, time and sorbate dose through batch method. The metal ion binding capacity and physical characteristics suggest that the material is suitable for solid phase extraction of lead ion from the effluent of battery, electroplating and pigment industries.

Keywords : Graft copolymerization, cross-linking, adsorption, selectivity.

Introduction

Among major toxic metals lead causes environmental problem when contaminated in soil and water¹ and accumulate to the food chain causes a serious threat². Lead mainly found as waste from vessels, pipes, gasoline additives, metal products, paints, pigments, storage battery industries. Lead inhibit the synthesis of hemoglobin³. Lead interferes with the biosynthesis of porphyrin⁴ (which is required in hemoglobin synthesis) by inhibiting the formation of porphobilinogen through interacting with the enzyme, delta-ALA (aminolevulinatase). Pb^{2+} co-coordinates with S and N sites of the enzyme. The level of delta-ALA gives a measure of lead content in blood. The lead contamination in blood (higher than 0.9 ppm) can produce anemia. Lead ion interfere the action of calcium ions and consequently bones are affected in lead poisoning. Pb^{2+} can damage the mitochondria of kidney allowing the loss of glucose, amino acids and phosphate through urine. At initial stage of lead poisoning, the lead is stored in the bones in a relatively inert form. But when body requires essential element like Ca and P, blood starts to leach out lead from bone and in these processes lead becomes available to manifest the ill effects⁵.

Several methods are describe for removal of lead ion such as solid phase extraction⁶, ion-exchange⁷, physical

adsorption⁸ etc. Metal ion adsorption on solid polymeric surface has now considered as a common techniques, because of its cost effectiveness, eco-friendliness and rapidness. The selectivity of these materials towards metal ion can be controlled by the immobilized functional group, pH of the medium, temperature, etc.

Maximum researchers are engaged in synthesizing suitable polymers having selective metal ion binding capacity. Very few of them^{9,10} reported removal and recovery of lead ion from aqueous solutions.

The above work deals with a new procedure for concentrating lead(II) ion by polymer of 4-styrene sulphonic monohydrate salt and cross-linked polyvinyl alcohol.

Experimental

Chemicals and reagents :

Polyvinyl alcohol (Burgoyne Burbidges, Mumbai, India, viscosity average molecular weight = 16100, degree of hydrolysis = 98.5–99 mol%), 4-styrene sulphonic monohydrate salt (StyS, 96% Aldrich), glutaraldehyde (Sp. gravity = 1.06 g/cc, Sd fine Chem., Ltd., Mol. wt. = 100.12), lead nitrate (Merck, Mumbai, India) and sulphuric acid (Merck, Mumbai, India, 98% Sp. gr. = 1.84, Mol. wt. = 98.08) were used as received.

Equipments :

Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra of the polymer were recorded on Shimadzu FTIR (Model No. 8400s) using KBr pellets. Thermal analysis was conducted using a Stanton Red Craft Thermal Analyzer (STA-780) in air at a rate of 10 °C/min. The amount of metal ion in the solution was measured using atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS, Shimadzu, AA 6300) and complexometrically. An Elico LI-120 pH meter, thermostat and chromatographic column (i.d. = 0.8 cm) were used.

Synthesis of cross-linked graft copolymer :

Graft copolymerization was carried out in a two-necked round-bottomed flask at 70 °C. A definite amount of polyvinyl alcohol (0.5 g) and 4-styrene sulphonic mono hydrate salt (2 g) was mixed with water (20 ml) and heated for 15 min; concentrated sulphuric acid (2 ml) and ceric ammonium sulphate (0.02 g) added to this mixture and stirred vigorously. Nitrogen atmosphere was maintained throughout the reaction period. After an hour glutaraldehyde (0.1 g) was mixed to cross-link the grafted product. Quenching with hydroquinone arrested polymerization and cross-linking reaction. The precipitated polymer was separated by filtration and washed several time with 1 : 10 H₂SO₄ (v/v). Finally, the sample was extracted with acetone for 72 h to dissolve all other impurities. The colorless product was dried under vacuum at 100 °C for 72 h to a constant weight. The yield was 5.2 g. The dried solid was grounded and screened through a set of sieves for the particles of the size ranged between 0.15 to 0.25 mm for conducting experiments.

Sorption and desorption procedure :

Adsorption by batch method was carried out with suitable mechanical agitation (90–100 rpm) and temperature (5 to 40 °C). To determine the retention of lead ion, 0.013 g of prepared polymer was taken into a 100 ml beaker with 10 ml metal solution. The concentration of lead(II) ion in aqueous solution was kept within 207 to 1242 mg/L (ppm).

The pH of the solution was maintained at 4.9. The selectivity of the prepared resin among various metal ions (Pb^{II}, Cd^{II} and Ni^{II}; commonly found in electroplating waste) were determined by a competitive batch method. Resin sample (0.013 g) was equilibrated for 60 min with 10 ml solution (3.3 ml of each metal ion solution, which

contained 0.001 mole metal ion). The adsorbed metal ions were sequentially eluted with the selective stripping agents.

Treatment of data :

All experiment was performed at room temperature (27 °C). The retention capacity (Q , mg/g), percentage of recovery (R), cross-link density (q) was calculated by following relation^{11–14}.

$$Q = \text{Metal ion adsorbed/adsorbent added} \quad (1)$$

$R = \text{Metal ion eluted (g)} \times 100/\text{metal ion originally bound to polymer.}$

$$q = M_o/M_c \quad (2)$$

M_o = Molecular weight of the repeating unit of polystyrene sulphonate.

M_c = Average molecular mass between consecutive cross-link¹⁴.

Results and discussion

Evidence for the formation of cross-linked graft copolymer :

FTIR spectra assignment of the cross-linked graft copolymer is shown in Fig. 1 exhibit all characteristics peaks of PVA. Peak at 3300 cm⁻¹, which is due to stretching of

Fig. 1. FTIR spectra of prepared polymer.

hydroxyl groups of SO₃H group and water molecule present in the sample. The band at 1300–1400 cm⁻¹ is due to stretching of S=O, also the band at 1100 cm⁻¹ is probably appear for O=S=O. The band at 1020 cm⁻¹ are due to ether linkage. By comparing all the peaks it should be concluded that copolymerization occurs¹⁵.

The trace of thermo gravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential analysis (DTA) of the prepared polymer shows two steps weight loss. First step (40–100 °C) weight loss is due to loss of water and second step weight loss (110–200 °C) may be attributed due to decomposition of the prepared polymer. The integral procedure decomposition temperature [IPDT] value¹⁶ of the prepared polymer is 420 °C which indicate that the prepared polymer is thermally stable.

Physical and chemical characteristic :

The physicochemical characteristics of the synthesized polymer are given in Table 1. The surface area of cross-linked polymer was determined by methylene blue adsorption method¹⁷ and was found to be 82.8 m²/g. The exchange capacity of the exchanger (3.5 meq H⁺/g) was superior to the literature value of commercially available many cation exchangers such as SRS-100 (1.85), VERSATIC-10 (2.11). The average molecular weight¹⁴, cross-link density and pore size (Å) of the material (prepared polymer) were 1345.8 g/mol, 0.048 and 56.54 Å respectively.

Table 1. Some physicochemical characteristics of the synthesized polymer

Parameters	Values	Measurement process
Bulk density (g/cc)	1.6	Specific gravity bottle
Particle size (mm)	0.25	Screened
Surface area (m ² /g)	82.8	Methylene blue adsorption method ¹³
Exchange capacity (meq H ⁺ /g)	3.5	Volumetric method ¹⁴
Average molecular weight between two cross-link (g/mol)	1345.8	Swelling studies ¹⁴
Cross-link density	0.048	Swelling studies ¹⁴
Pore size (Å)	56.54	Swelling studies ¹⁴
Percentage of grafting (g)	10	Chemical ¹⁴

Influence of pH on lead ion retention :

Fig. 3 shows Pb^{II} ion retention on the cross-linked graft polymer as a function of the pH of solution. It shows that the retention amount of Pb^{II} increases with the increase of solution pH, the retention process is full pH-dependent. The optimum pH was found to be 4.9.

The lead ion goes to the exchange site by ion exchange process [eq. (3)]. The exchangeable hydrogen ion

Fig. 2. TGA and DTA of prepared polymer.

Fig. 3. Pb^{II} retention capacity at different pH (sorbent dose = 1.3 mg/L, sorbate dose = 202 mg/L, time = 1 h, temperature = 27 °C).

favors the ion exchange process.

At low pH solution (<4.9), the equilibrium shifts towards left and less amount of lead ion absorbed. While at higher pH (>4.9) lead ion undergoes hydrolysis and stop the adsorption process. So the optimum pH for metal ion adsorption by this prepared polymer is 4.9.

Effect of sorbate dose on metal adsorption :

Fig. 4 shows the sorbate dose effect on adsorption of Pb^{II} by keeping the other conditions (pH = 4.9, temperature = 27 °C, sorbent dose = 1.3 g/L and time = 1 h) fixed. It was observed that lead ion uptake capacity of the sorbent increases sharply with the increase of metal ion concentration. The lead ion retention capacity of the resin

Fig. 4. Effect of sorbate dose on its adsorption (sorbent dose = 1.3 mg/L, sorbate dose = 207 mg/L, time = 1 h, temperature = 27 °C, pH = 4.9).

was 11.8 mg/g at low level of sorbate (207 ppm) and became 49 mg/g at 1000 ppm of lead. The maximum uptake capacity was found to be 200 mg/g at relatively higher dose of sorbate (4800 ppm).

Effect of temperature and adsorption thermodynamics :

The effect of temperature on Pb^{II} adsorption at various sorbate dose is shown in Fig. 5. The adsorption capacity increases with the increasing temperature from 5 to 40 °C and then decreases with further increase of temperature. The adsorption and desorption occurred through

Fig. 5. Variation of adsorption with time at different temperature (sorbent dose = 1.3 g/L, sorbate dose = 207 ppm, pH = 4.9, time = 1 h; (1) 5 °C, (2) 27 °C, (3) 40 °C).

Scheme 1. Formation of cross-linked grafted polymer.

ion exchange process. Initial increase of temperature favors the adsorption, while increase of temperature above 40 °C accelerates the desorption process.

Retention of Pb^{II} in the competitive condition :

In this group of experiments, the competitive sorption of nickel, cadmium, mercury, lead and zinc ions onto the polymer were investigated. These experiments were performed at a constant pH (4.9), temperature (27 °C), sorbent dose (1.3 g/L) and time (1 h) with the solution containing 0.001 mole of each metal ion. The selectivity¹⁸ of the polymer for the metal (M₁) ion with respect to the competitive metal (M₂) ions was determined according to the following relationship :

$$S = \log K_d(M_1) - \log K_d(M_2) \quad (4)$$

where the distribution coefficients (K_d) of metal ions between the sorbent phase and sorption medium at equilibrium, was calculated by using the following expression :

K_d = The amount of metal ion in mg adsorbed per g of the polymer/The amount of metal ion in mg present per mL of the solution.

The selectivity of the polymer for Pb^{II} with respect to Ni^{II} , Cd^{II} , Zn^{II} and Hg^{II} are 0.13, 0.22, 0.05 and 0.04. The positive values of selectivity indicate that the prepared material binds preferably Pb^{II} ion in presence of Ni^{II} , Cd^{II} , Zn^{II} and Hg^{II} ions.

Method of Pb^{II} separation and its analytical application :

It was possible to separate Pb^{II} ion from several metal ions present in a binary mixture by using selective stripping agents. Each binary mixture was prepared by mixing an aliquot of standard solution of Pb^{II} (2.17 mg/L) and one of the diverse metal ions at desired pH (Table 2, A to D). At pH 4.9 Ni^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} were co-extracted quantitatively along with Pb^{II} from their respective binary mixtures. Pb^{II} was first eluted from the column with the help of 0.01 M of HNO_3 from mixture A and then Ni^{II} was desorbed by 0.02 M of H_2SO_4 . Similarly other diverse metal ions were separated from Pb^{II} using diffe-

rent eluents as shown in Table 2 (B to D). The amount of eluent required for separation of each metal ion was given in the table. After recovery, metal ions were determined complex metrically.

In order to assess the analytical application the proposed method was applied to separate Pb^{II} from multi component synthetic mixture (Table 2, E to F) containing lead with different metal ions commonly coming from electroplating waste belong in the same analytical group.

Application of the developed method in real sample :

In order to evaluate the accuracy and applicability of the proposed method for analysis of real environmental samples, it was applied to determination of lead ion in tap, well and electroplating waste samples. Aqueous solution (100 ml) of samples having known concentration of Pb^{II} ion at pH 4.9 was passed through the column at the flow rate of 1.0 ml/min. The extracted lead ion was eluted with minimum volume of 0.01 M of HNO_3 and subjected to the determination of lead content by AAS (Table 3). Data indicates that the proposed method is highly sensitive and the pre-concentration procedure is applicable to determine lead up to ppb levels and can be used for estimation of lead in environmental samples.

Table 2. Separation of Pb^{II} from synthetic mixture

Mixture	Cations	Added (mg)	Recovered (mg)	RSD (%)	Eluent (M) mL
A	Pb^{II}	2.20	2.18	4.80	0.010 M HNO_3 (80)
	Hg^{II}	2.15	1.90	2.50	0.050 M H_2SO_4 (20)
B	Pb^{II}	2.20	2.19	3.80	0.010 M HNO_3 (80)
	Ni^{II}	2.18	1.95	1.60	0.005 M H_2SO_4 (30)
C	Pb^{II}	2.20	2.12	3.40	0.010 M HNO_3 (80)
	Cd^{II}	2.62	1.98	1.70	0.005 M HNO_3 (50)
D	Pb^{II}	2.20	2.15	3.20	0.010 M HNO_3 (80)
	Zn^{II}	2.10	1.75	1.25	0.005 M H_2SO_4 (45)
E	Pb^{II}	2.20	2.19	3.10	0.010 M HNO_3 (80)
	Cd^{II}	2.62	1.98	1.60	0.005 M HNO_3 (40)
	Zn^{II}	2.10	1.75	1.25	0.005 M H_2SO_4 (50)
F	Pb^{II}	2.20	2.19	4.80	0.010 M HNO_3 (80)
	Ni^{II}	2.18	1.95	1.54	0.005 M H_2SO_4 (50)
	Hg^{II}	2.15	1.90	2.50	0.050 M H_2SO_4 (40)

Column : Internal diameter = 0.08 cm, bed height = 8 cm, flow rate = 1 mL/min, pH = 4.9 and temperature = 27 °C.

Table 3. Determination of lead(II) ion in environmental samples

Environmental samples	Pb ^{II} added (µg/L)	Pb ^{II} ion found by AAS (µg/L)	Recovery (%)
Tap water	0	6.9 ± 0.5	-
	10	16.6 ± 0.8	100
	50	55.2 ± 1.2	98
Well water	0	2.9 ± 0.3	-
	10	12.6 ± 0.6	97
	50	51.2 ± 0.8	99
Electroplating waste	0	12.2 ± 0.6	-
	10	18.6 ± 0.9	100
	50	58.2 ± 1.8	98

Conclusion :

For its high exchange capacity the prepared polymer can be used as a cation exchanger. It has good chemical and thermal stability. Exchange bed could be used more than 30 cycles with little loss of exchange capacity. The developed technique could be applied for the selective extraction of lead ion from environmental samples. The proposed method is highly efficient, cost effective, simple and rapid. The cross-linked polymer of PVA and 4-styrene sulphonic monohydrate salt has significantly higher lead ion uptake capacity and selectivity than that of PVA.

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